

IRISCC

D8.3 Description of user support and feedback system

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Abstract

Key words	User, Access, Support, Feedback loop, Service provision.
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This deliverable presents the design, components, and operational workflow of the IRISCC user support and feedback system, developed within Work Package 8 “IRISCC TA and VA access management” to facilitate efficient, user-friendly access to IRISCC services. The system ensures that researchers working on climate change risks receive clear information and timely assistance both for Transnational Access (TA) and Virtual Access (VA). Based on a tiered helpdesk approach, the support system includes resources for self-help, general assistance, and specialised scientific and technical guidance provided by the IRISCC installations. It is completed by a specific user feedback loop, which is intended to ensure alignment with user needs and continuous improvement of processes and services based on user comments, suggestions and recommendations. Roles and responsibilities across the various IRISCC actors are clearly mapped using a RASCI matrix, ensuring transparent ownership of tasks and efficient coordination among all staff involved.

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D8.3 Description of user support and feedback system

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Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
Access	The legitimate and authorised physical, remote and virtual admission to, interactions with and use of Research Infrastructures and to services offered by Research Infrastructures to users
CoS	Catalogue of Services
D	Deliverable (of the project)
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FAQ	Frequently asked questions
KPI	Key Performance Indicators, major quantifiable indicators of progress toward an intended result that create an analytical basis for decision-making supporting strategic and operational improvement.
MS	Milestone (of the project)
PASS	Platform for managing user Access to ACTRIS Services (PASS), an online, centralised access management platform operated by the ACTRIS Service and Access Management Unit and made available to IRISCC to manage physical, remote and hybrid access to the research facilities.
PC	Project Coordination
RASCI	Responsible, Acknowledging, Supportive, Consulted, Informed (RASCI) matrix, a chart used to help clearly identify roles and responsibilities within a team or organisation on a project.
RI	Research Infrastructure, defined in the EU Charter of access to Research Infrastructures as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. They include major scientific equipment (or sets of instruments), knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives and scientific data, e-infrastructures, such as data and computing systems and communication networks and any other tools that are essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation. They may be 'single-sited', 'virtual' and 'distributed'”.
SAMU	Service and Access Management Unit of the ACTRIS ERIC Head Office
TA	Transnational access (physical, remote, hybrid)

TA - Physical access	Physical access is “hands-on” access when users physically visit an infrastructure/facility/equipment/installation. Physical access means access to services offered by IRISCC through an installation of the participating RIs. The available services or resources are not unlimited, and a competitive, peer-reviewed process is required following a defined procedure with well-defined criteria and call conditions for the selection of users.
TA - Remote access	Remote access is access to resources and services offered by IRISCC through participating RIs without users physically visiting the infrastructure/facility/equipment/installation. Similar to physical access, the services or resources are not unlimited, and a competitive, peer-reviewed process is required following a defined procedure with well-defined criteria and call conditions for the selection of users.
TA - Hybrid access	Hybrid access combines multiple types of access to IRISCC resources and services, including virtual, physical and remote access. As hybrid involves resources for which the IRISCC facilities have limited capacity, a competitive selection of users similar to that described above for physical and remote access is required.
T&S	User’s travel and subsistence
User	A person, a team, or an institution from any sector, including the public and private sector making use of RI data or other services, including access to the RI facilities.
VA	Virtual access (VA) is free access to users provided by a facility or infrastructure through communication networks; an unlimited number of users can simultaneously use the available services or resources, and the users are not selected. Virtual access within IRISCC concerns access to scientific data, digital tools and/or integrated online services related to climate change risks.
WP	Work Package, a component of the project work breakdown representing a manageable unit of work within a project, including a major group of project activities targeting common specific objectives.

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Executive summary

This deliverable provides a comprehensive description of the IRISCC user support and feedback system established within Work Package 8 (WP8) “IRISCC TA and VA access management” to ensure effective, user-centric facilitation of Transnational Access (TA) and Virtual Access (VA) to IRISCC services.

The system addresses the diverse needs of researchers working on climate change related multi-hazard risks, who often operate in interdisciplinary contexts and require integrated scientific, technical, and operational assistance, while also supporting other key actors involved with climate change risks, such as local authorities, public agencies, practitioners, companies and community stakeholders. Importantly, the support is available to all interested potential users, not only to those who formally apply to access specific services.

The support framework is organised into four key components: the TA Helpdesk, the VA Helpdesk, the General Support function, and the IRISCC user feedback loop. Each component contributes to a coherent and accessible support system enabling users and service providers to access clear information, obtain timely assistance, and engage in consistent communication throughout all stages of the access lifecycle. The TA helpdesk, already operational and described in detail, implements a multi-tiered model combining self-support resources, general support, and specialised technical assistance provided by installation staff.

A central part of the system is the structured user feedback loop, which captures user experiences through multiple channels, categorises the input, and routes it to the relevant IRISCC actors for evaluation and action. This ensures that user-driven insights support service improvement, operational optimisation, and long-term development of IRISCC access processes.

To guarantee clarity and accountability, the deliverable introduces a RASCI matrix clearly showing responsibilities assigned to WP8, WP9 “VA01 – Virtual access provision for climate change risk services”, WP10 “TA01 – Transnational access provision for climate change risk services”, WP1 “Communication, dissemination, engagement, and exploitation management”, the IRISCC Project Coordination, and the IRISCC Executive Board. This structure clearly identifies who is responsible, accountable, consulted, supportive, or informed for each task, ensuring transparency and efficient collaboration across the consortium.

1 Introduction

This document describes the system to prepare, encourage and support the use and provision of the IRISCC services, which has been implemented to increase user engagement and reinforce the project user-centric approach for access and service development.

The report is prepared in the framework of the IRISCC project (Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change risks), which supports challenge-driven and interdisciplinary research on climate-change-related multi-hazard risks. This deliverable D8.3 summarises the work carried out in Work Package (WP) 8 “IRISCC TA and VA access management” for Task 8.3 “Transnational and virtual access related service user and service provider support”.

The system was designed in line with the recommendations proposed in Deliverable 6.3 “Guidelines on proposed harmonisation measures for TA policies and procedures for the service provision” [R1] and implemented before the launch of the first TA Call in April 2025. It has continued to evolve since then, with new resources added to streamline the provision of support and improve the user journey.

The document outlines the current configuration of the user support system at the time of this deliverable’s release. It is structured into six sections. Following the introduction, Section 2 describes the mission assigned to the user support system. Section 3 presents its main components, while the subsequent sections provide detailed descriptions of the helpdesks for Transnational Access (TA), Virtual Access (VA) and general inquiries. Section 4 explains the process for collecting and processing feedback from users, and Section 5 summarises the roles and responsibilities involved. Finally, Section 6 provides the list of references consulted.

2 Mission of the IRISCC user support and feedback system

The IRISCC user support and feedback system consists of a set of tools and practices studied to fulfil the needs for information and assistance of IRISCC providers as well as actual or potential users, enabling them to, respectively, efficiently provide scientific services and conduct excellent research in climate change risks. The system also ensures that their feedback is distributed to provide input for continuous improvements of the services and of the access management process.

The coordinated, efficient functioning of the system guarantees that IRISCC continues to meet users' expectations effectively, assisting and contributing to decision-making based on key input and feedback from users channelled to the relevant actors to take targeted action.

The user support system is intended to:

- a. help users obtaining complete, clear and practical information on the available services and access opportunities. This is particularly important as climate change risks actors are engaged in multi/interdisciplinary studies and require integrated support when working across scientific, technical, environmental, and socioeconomic domains.
- b. to provide quick, efficient and attentive assistance to help users achieve their scientific/technical goals using IRISCC resources.
- c. to introduce and maintain appropriate feedback loops to capture, store, process and follow-up on user reviews, suggestion, comments, proposals, etc.

As for the scope, the support system shall cover all inquiries related to:

- ✓ Transnational Access (TA)
- ✓ Virtual Access (VA)
- ✓ General project-related matters

Ultimately, the objective is to create an organized environment that enables *all* users to communicate any IRISCC- related doubt, problem, or issue they have and, at the same time, allows for the relevant actors to quickly and efficiently respond to reported issues.

3 Main components

Following the mission assigned to the IRISCC support and feedback system, its scope and the key functions it must perform, the system's main components and features are identified as:

1. TA Helpdesk
2. VA Helpdesk
3. IRISCC General support
4. IRISCC User feedback loop

as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Functions, components and roles of the IRISCC User support and feedback system

IRISCC User support and feedback system		
Functions	Components	Responsible
Provide quick, efficient and attentive assistance to users for Access	TA Helpdesk (physical, remote, hybrid access)	WP8/SAMU Team
	VA helpdesk (virtual access)	WP8/CNRS Team
Offer clear information, initial guidance, and timely assistance for all project-related matters to all interested parties.	IRISCC General support	IRISCC Coordination
Introduce and maintain appropriate set of processes to collect, process and follow up on user reviews, suggestion, comments, proposals, etc.	IRISCC User feedback system	WP8 Teams + relevant IRISCC actors

The objective is to create an organized environment that enables *all* users to communicate any IRISCC- related doubt, problem, or issue they have and, at the same time, allows for the relevant actors to quickly and efficiently respond to reported issues.

The helpdesk function is accessible from:

- **PASS** (TA management tool, described in R2)
- **VA management tool** (described in R3)
- **IRISCC website**

Each entry point displays the dedicated email address (helpdesk@iriscc.eu) established to centralise the collection of support requests and ensure re-routing to the appropriate

actor for response. Where possible, the entry points provide a direct link for submitting requests.

The user support system is closely integrated with the IRISCC communication and dissemination activities (WPI). Information on available support channels is communicated through the IRISCC website, access programme guidance materials, webinars for applicants, and other project communication channels. This ensures that potential users can easily identify where to obtain assistance throughout the access lifecycle.

3.1 TA helpdesk

The TA helpdesk is built around the support function centrally managed by the WP8 TA Team and involves various IRISCC actors.

It is implemented as a tiered system where solution of issues can be easily escalated (Figure 1).

Figure 1. IRISCC tiered TA Helpdesk

WP8 TA Team coordinates support provided at different levels, walking users through problem-solving process whenever they have questions or issues about access to IRISCC services, following up with users to ensure the issue has been resolved and soliciting feedback.

TIER 1 is Self-support through the TA Knowledge Base, maintained and widely disseminated in cooperation with WPI (Communication, dissemination, engagement, and exploitation management). This tier is based on the consideration that people in most cases prefer to find answers on their own and applies the “Learn by yourself” principle, which both empowers users and reduces the number of requests to be handled by other Tiers.

The **TA Knowledge Base** is offered on two complementary forms:

- the **IRISCC Website**, providing general information on access opportunities, including introductory guidance intended for a broad audience of potential users
- the **TA management platform (PASS)** offering more detailed and operational resources, such as workflows descriptions, templates, criteria, step-by-step instructions, and video tutorials.

The **IRISCC website** offers the following resources on access provided by IRISCC:

- **Information on the sponsored access offered**
- Details on the **TA, VA** and fast-track access options
- Introduction and access point to the IRISCC Service Catalogue
- General presentation on the IRISCC Access Programme
- Guidelines and materials, like the **IRISCC Transnational & Virtual Access Handbook** and recorded **webinars on how to discover and access IRISCC Services**
- Frequently asked questions about access (**<https://www.iriscc.eu/faq>**)

The **TA knowledge base available on PASS** offers self-support resources for users:

- Video resources to offer visual **Introduction to ACCESS**, as well as walkthroughs, and demonstrations designed to help understand processes faster and apply them with confidence (**User application phase**)
- **IRISCC Guidelines for applicants**
- **IRISCC TA Application Form**
- **IRISCC TA General Evaluation Guidelines**
- **IRISCC User Acknowledgement of Access Terms**
- **IRISCC User Final Activity Report template**
- **IRISCC User Feedback**

as well as self-support resources for providers:

- **IRISCC Provider Feasibility Form**
- **IRISCC Provider Confirmation of Access**
- two video resources offering visual explanations of the key tasks for providers in the access process (**Provider feasibility check** and **Provider confirmation of access**)

TIER 2 is the general information and assistance on physical, remote and hybrid access that does not need specific technical know-how. Such support is provided by the WP8 TA and IRISCC Coordination Teams, which handle requests coming from any interested people, users, providers and peer reviewers that are related to the access process (applications, eligibility, feasibility, evaluation process, criteria, scoring, ranking, travel support etc.), the access platform and, in general, all support requests not directly linked to service specific topics. Such support activities mainly involve:

- ✓ Responding to queries via chat, email, or phone.
- ✓ Supporting users with the online submission of their requests for access.

- Following the requirements of the Horizon Europe funding call [R4], special dedicated support is available for **Ukrainian researchers** who may need assistance in preparing applications for the access calls. They may contact the TA Team to receive appropriate support, either directly or, where relevant, through the Principal Investigator of the corresponding installation
- ✓ Providing any additional information needed and requested
- ✓ Checking on users during the access.

TIER 3 is the level where specific information and assistance on services, which requires advanced, domain-specific knowledge, is granted by the staff of the relevant installation. IRISCC providers in fact are both recipients of the support and providers of operational support within the TA helpdesk system. While they receive assistance for all aspects of the access process (feasibility assessments, use of the PASS platform, access reporting, financial reporting, and related matters), they also constitute the second core actor of the support structure.

Providers are responsible for addressing and resolving all support that is either:

- Requested directly to them by users during the access phase, or
- Requested via PASS or email and transferred to them by the WP8 TA Team when the issue concerns scientific, technical, or service-specific aspects.

In addition, as mentioned above, providers offer **dedicated support to Ukrainian users**, including assistance in preparing their Transnational Access proposals.

3.2 VA helpdesk

User support for VA services follows a distributed model, reflecting the diversity of services provided by the different Research Infrastructures acting as service providers. While general information about the IRISCC Access Programme and the available VA services is made available through the project's central communication channels (e.g. the IRISCC website and access platform), the operational user support related to the use of individual services is primarily ensured by the respective service providers. This approach allows support to be tailored to the specific technical characteristics, user communities, and operational requirements of each service.

Depending on the service and on the practices adopted by the corresponding Research Infrastructure, several types of support mechanisms may be offered to users. These may include direct contact via email, online contact forms, frequently asked questions (FAQ), documentation pages, written guides or video tutorials, and in some cases structured helpdesk or ticketing systems. Such resources are intended to help users understand how to access and use the services effectively, while enabling service providers to deliver appropriate technical assistance when needed.

3.3 IRISCC General Support

The IRISCC Project Coordination (PC) is the main contact point for internal and external actors related to general IRISCC inquiries. The Coordination team provides basic information on project activities and connects external and internal stakeholders as needed. It also handles the day-to-day management of the project and oversees the progress and budget expenditure. IRISCC General support, including also guidance for TA and VA users and providers, is available via project's main email address: IRISCC-Coordination@luke.fi. This address is visible in project website and included in digital and printed materials (e.g. newsletter and flyers).

As the TA and VA helpdesk become increasingly visible and widely used, the role of Coordination in TA/VA user support is expected to decrease. However, it remains relevant for requests and questions related to the management of the user Travel and Subsistence (T&S) contribution.

For this purpose, the Coordination has a specific role within TA helpdesk Tier 2, described in Section 3.1, where it supports users and providers in handling, receiving and reporting the T&S support. When relevant, the Coordination team forwards the request to the WP8 TA Team, to the VA helpdesk or directly to service provider.

3.4 User feedback process

An efficient, user-friendly process for collecting and handling feedback on TA and VA activities has been implemented to enable assessment from both users and providers. This allows IRISCC to improve access management and enhance its services based on the perspectives, experiences, and suggestions of all parties involved.

The process designed draws on a standard customer feedback loop, which has been adapted to IRISCC TA/VA activities. The main actors involved, with different roles depending on their responsibilities in IRISCC, are:

- a) the User community, providing feedback
- b) the WP8 Team, collecting and distributing the feedback in Task 8.4
- c) the IRISCC Executive Board (EB)
- d) IRISCC WP9 and WP10
- e) the relevant IRISCC installation or data center providing the TA or VA service

The timely routing of user feedback to the appropriate WPs for its follow-up is necessary to maintain quality and gain user trust.

Figure 2. IRISCC User feedback loop & services enhancement process, which illustrates the main steps of the loop, which are:

1. Feedback collection, with any available and possible means:
 - First and foremost, with the User feedback forms specifically built in PASS and in the VA Portal. In case of TA, users must fill in and submit the feedback form

after completion of the access at the installation as part of post-access requirements.

- Helpdesk interactions
- email
- personal contacts.

2. Feedback sharing: the WP8 Team stores and arranges the feedback into homogeneous and agreed KPI categories, making a preliminary evaluation to identify the relevant actors and reroute the feedback for follow-up action. Feedback is shared with the EB and the identified relevant WPs.

3-5 Reflection on feedback and action: a joint evaluation on the reasons for both negative and positive comments to identify suitable actions to follow up on the feedback is promoted within the IRISCC EB. Relevant actors (EB, WP 8-9-10 leaders, Installations and data centers) decide together what to do, when and how to act, and then put decisions into practice following user feedback.

The feedback loop is not closed but continuous to ensuring that IRISCC services and access management processes remain relevant to users and suitable to fulfil their needs. User feedback also contributes to the continuous improvement of communication materials and user guidance resources maintained under WP1, including website, FAQ page, and Access Handbook. This ensures that recurring user questions and challenges are addressed through clearer guidance and improved information resources.

Figure 2. IRISCC User feedback loop & services enhancement process

5 Roles and responsibilities

A RASCI (Responsible, Accountable, Supportive, Consulted, Informed) matrix was created to help identify the key roles and responsibilities in operating the IRISCC user support and feedback system.

The following roles were identified and proposed for attribution:

- **Responsible:** the person or team who does the work and is responsible for the correct execution of the task.
- **Accountable:** the team that owns the activity, validates it and is ultimately accountable for it.
- **Supportive:** who helps to complete the work.
- **Consulted:** who provides input and advice.
- **Informed:** who is informed about developments and outcomes.

The following relevant actors and stakeholders were identified to distribute roles to:

- WP8 Team, IRISCC TA and VA access management
- WP9 Team, VA01 - Virtual access provision for climate change risk services
- WP10 Team, TA01 - Transnational access provision for climate change risk services
- WP1 Team, Communication, dissemination, engagement, and exploitation management
- PC, the IRISCC Project Coordination
- EB, the IRISCC Executive Board

The resulting RASCI matrix is reported in Table 2. The responsibilities indicated were taken on and have been actively fulfilled by the relevant actors since the beginning of the system implementation, well before any formal role definition was finalised in this document.

Escalation Details:

- 1) For TA support requests requiring advanced, domain specific knowledge, WP8 (TA Team/SAMU) escalates to WP10 (TA Provider). During T3 work, WP10 is Responsible/Accountable for the scientific and technical support; WP8 remains Supportive and Informed for coordination and user updates.
- 2) For VA support requests requiring specific know-how on the service, WP8 (CNRS) escalates to WP9 (VA Provider) under the same pattern (WP9 = Responsible/Accountable during technical resolution).
- 3) PC remains Informed during routine support activities and may be Consulted during major requests or policy/priority decisions.
- 4) EB is periodically Informed just for oversight and consulted only when strategic steering is required.

Table 2: RASCI matrix for the IRISCC user support and feedback system

	WP8 TA Team	WP8 VA Team	WP9	WP10	WP1	PC	EB
1. TA Helpdesk	A/R	I		R	S	S	I
Knowledge base update (TIER 1)	R			C	S	I	
Support request intake (TIER 2)	R				S	S	
Categorisation and triage	R				I	I	
First response & Resolution (TIER 2)	R					S	
Escalation to provider (if needed)	R			I			
Scientific/technical Resolution & closure (TIER 3)	I			R/A			
Request intake & resolution during access (TIER 3)	S			R/A			
2. VA Helpdesk	I	A/R	R		I	I	I
Support request intake (email/portal/etc.)		R					
Categorisation and triage		R	C				
First response & Resolution		R					
Escalation to provider (if needed)		R	I				
Scientific/technical Resolution & closure			R				
3. IRISCC General Support	S	S	S	S	S	A/R	I
General enquiry intake and routing	S/R	S	S	S	S	R	
Cross-project guidance and referrals	C	C	C	C		R	
Providing general project information					S	R	

R	Responsible
A	Accountable
S	Supportive
C	Consulted
I	Informed

6 References

Reference	
No	Description/Link
R1.	IRISCC Deliverable D6.3 – Guidelines on proposed harmonisation measures for TA policies and procedures for the service provision. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14247535
R2.	IRISCC D8.1 Optimized IRISCC Transnational Access Management Tool. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15357943
R3.	IRISCC D8.2 Optimised IRISCC VA Management System. https://doi.org/10.5281/10.5281/zenodo.15592864
R4.	HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01-01 Research infrastructure services to enable R&I addressing main challenges and EU priorities. https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/HORIZON_HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01-01 (visited 30.3.2026)